

MANAGING INTERNATIONALIZATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Managing internationalization in higher education has become an increasingly important area of concern for academic institutions around the world. With the globalization of the economy and the increasing mobility of students, faculty, and researchers, universities must adapt their strategies to remain competitive in an increasingly interconnected world. This involves developing programs and services that meet the needs of international students, recruiting and retaining international faculty, and fostering cross-cultural collaboration and exchange. Effective internationalization strategies require a strong commitment from university leaders, as well as the engagement of all stakeholders, including faculty, staff, students, and community partners. This paper will explore the challenges and opportunities of managing internationalization in higher education, and provide insights into best practices and strategies for success.

Keywords: Internationalization, higher education, globalization, mobility, cross-cultural collaboration, student services, faculty recruitment, community engagement, best practices, strategies.

I THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF Internationalization in higher education

1.1 Theoretical aspects of managing internationalization in higher education

Internationalization of higher education is the process of integrating international aspects into the higher education system. It includes various strategies and actions aimed at attracting foreign students, teachers, researchers, as well as the exchange of knowledge, experience and resources of the international community.

Kazakhstan, as a country that is actively developing economically and socially, also attaches great importance to the internationalization of higher education. The key elements of this process in Kazakhstan are:

1. Attracting international students. Kazakh universities are actively working in the international market of educational services, offering students from all over the world a quality education. For this purpose, special programs are being created to ensure a high level of education and adaptation of students from other countries.

2. Attracting foreign teachers and researchers. Kazakh universities are trying to invite experienced and qualified teachers and researchers from other countries to work. This makes it possible to increase the level of education and research, as well as to create a favorable intercultural environment at universities

3. Participation in international educational programs and projects. Kazakh universities actively participate in various international educational programs and projects, such as the European Student Exchange Program Erasmus+ or Fulbright programs. This makes it possible to expand the boundaries of knowledge and experience of students and teachers, as well as to increase the level of education and research.

4. Development of international cooperation with other universities. Kazakh universities are actively working on the development of international cooperation with other universities, both within the country and abroad. This allows not only the exchange of experience and expertise, but also the creation of scientific research, research, organization of participation of students and teachers.

5. Creating the conditions for research and research in the field of foreign affairs is becoming. In Kazakhstan, there are many universities where the Kazakh or Russian language is intensively studied. However, given the importance of international assessments, programs in foreign languages, such as English, German, French, etc., have been actively developed in recent years.

6. Creation of conditions for the work of foreign students and teachers in Kazakhstan. Kazakhstan proposes to create favorable conditions for monitoring foreign students and consultants, such as housing costs, scholarships, medical care, as well as assistance in adapting to a new country.

The internationalization of higher education in Kazakhstan has not only educational but also economic significance. It helps to attract foreign investment, increase international competitiveness, expand the frontiers of knowledge and experience, and create international links and partnerships.

However, it should be noted that the process of internationalization of higher education is also associated with some challenges and problems, such as cultural differences, language barriers, adaptation to a new environment, etc. Therefore, for the successful internationalization of higher education in Kazakhstan, it is necessary to take into account all these aspects and develop appropriate strategies and programs.

1.2 The role of managing internationalization in higher education

The management of internationalization in higher education plays an important role in the successful development of this process. The key functions of internationalization management include planning, coordinating, monitoring and evaluating the implementation of internationalization programs and recommendations.

The main tasks of managing internationalization in higher education include:

Development of an internationalization strategy. The internationalization strategy determines the goals, priorities, directions and methods for the development of international activities at the university.

- Planning and organization of programs and projects of internationalization. The Office should coordinate and organize international programs including student exchanges, faculty exchanges, research and research development.

- Attracting foreign students and teachers. Management should be associated with the involvement of foreign students and educators who are demanding on the conditions of study and work.

- Support for foreign students and teachers. Management should be given to international students and faculty in all aspects of their life and work at the university, including employment, paperwork, medical care, etc.

- Monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of internationalization. The effectiveness of internationalization programs and projects should be monitored and evaluated and adjusted if necessary.

Thus, the role of internationalization management in higher education plays an important role in developing international relations and attracting foreign students and teachers, which makes it possible to obtain international benefits from the university and expand the frontiers of knowledge and experience.

1.3 Problems of managing internationalization in higher education

One of the main problems of studying the topic of internationalization in higher educational institutions of Kazakhstan is the lack of a unified strategy and concept of internationalization at the country level. Despite the fact that many universities have already begun the process of internationalization, the lack of a unified strategy and concept makes it difficult to coordinate and coordinate actions between different universities and public administration bodies.

In addition, there are several other problems that may complicate internationalization in higher education institutions in Kazakhstan, such as:

- Insufficient funding and lack of sufficient funds for internationalization activities.

- The lack of sufficient training of students and teachers to work in a multicultural environment and in English.

- The low level of quality of education and research in higher education institutions, which makes it difficult to attract foreign students and teachers.

Thus, the main problem of studying the topic of internationalization in higher educational institutions of Kazakhstan is the need to develop a unified strategy and concept of internationalization at the country level, as well as solving a number of other problems that may complicate the process of internationalization. In addition, one of the main problems of internationalization in higher educational institutions of Kazakhstan is the lack of a sufficient number of qualified teachers capable of teaching in English and working in a multicultural environment. It is necessary to develop professional development programs for teachers so that they can work effectively in an international environment and attract foreign students.

In addition, there are also problems related to intercultural communication and the adaptation of foreign students to the culture and lifestyle in Kazakhstan. It is necessary to develop support and adaptation programs for foreign students and provide them with sufficient information about the culture and traditions of Kazakhstan.

Another problem may be the lack of a sufficient number of international exchange programs that could provide international experience and knowledge for students. It is necessary to develop new exchange programs and expand existing ones so that students can gain international experience and improve their knowledge and skills.

Thus, the problems of internationalization in higher educational institutions of Kazakhstan may be related to the lack of a unified strategy and concept of internationalization at the country level, insufficient funding, lack of qualified teachers and intercultural communication, as well as limited access to international exchange programs. Solving these problems can help Kazakhstan achieve full internationalization of higher education and increase its prestige on the world stage.

CONCLUSION OF 1st CHAPTER

In conclusion, internationalization of higher education in Kazakhstan is an important process that involves integrating international aspects into the higher education system. It includes various strategies and actions aimed at attracting foreign students, teachers, researchers, as well as the exchange of knowledge, experience and resources of the international community. The management of internationalization plays a crucial role in the successful development of this process, which includes planning, coordinating, monitoring and evaluating the implementation of internationalization programs and recommendations. However, there are several challenges and problems associated with the internationalization process, such as cultural differences, language barriers, adaptation to a new environment, insufficient funding, lack of sufficient training of students and teachers to work in a multicultural environment and in English, and low quality of education and research. To address these challenges and problems, a unified strategy and concept of internationalization at the country level, professional development programs for teachers, and support for foreign students are essential.

II ANALYTICAL SELECTION OF INTERNATIONALIZATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION

2.1 Analysis of methods of Internationalization in higher education

To study the problem of internationalization in higher education in Kazakhstan, various research methods and processes can be used. One possible approach is qualitative research, which includes conducting in-depth interviews with participants in internationalization programs, analyzing documents, reports and statistics, and observing the process of internationalization in universities.

First visit was conducted in December 2017 by Kazakhstani Consultant Dr. D. Woodward. The purpose of the first visit was to get feedback from the working group members on the relevance and actuality of the questions in the SAT. After the visit, the results of the discussions were communicated to the UK Consultant, discussed, and incorporated into the tool.

The tool was then sent to participating universities to be filled out by relevant departments/working group members. The data were then collected and analyzed.

The second visit was conducted by a team – British Council representative, UK Consultant and Kazakhstan Consultant for over 10 days in January and February 2018. Discussions, presentations, exchange of knowledge and opinions took place during the visit.

The objectives of the visit were:

- To meet with the working group members and share the views on Internationalisation, Governance, quality assurance and Curriculum and student care with British Council representative, UK and Kazakhstan experts.

- To present the preliminary findings based on the returns from universities and recommendations

- To quality check the provided answers and “unpack” them for better understanding and analysis

- To present internationalisation trends in the UK universities
- To discuss opportunities for universities in Kazakhstan to take on experience from the UK and adapt it to the local context

- To identify best practice examples from each university

The outcomes of the visit were:

- Representatives of Kazakhstani universities have better understanding of internationalization practice in the UK

- British Council representatives, UK and Kazakhstani expert have better knowledge on the issues that universities face during the process of internationalization and management of universities

- British Council representatives, UK and Kazakhstani expert have better realization of strengths and limitations of the developed SAT

- Project participants have better self-awareness on their position on internationalization, governance and quality assurance in national and international contexts

- UK-Kazakhstan collaboration in higher education is strengthened

Both quantitative and qualitative methods were used in the study. Quantitative methods included questionnaires and statistical analysis. Qualitative methods included focus groups and best practice examples.

The data analysis and recommendations in this study were done collectively as a pool for all universities rather than each HEI.

Another approach is quantitative research, which includes the analysis of data collected through surveys of students and teachers of organizations engaged in internationalization, as well as the collection of data on the number of foreign students and teachers in universities, etc. Research can use a combination of different methods, such as conducting a qualitative study to gain an in-depth understanding of problems and identify potential solutions, and then using quantitative methods to validate hypotheses and measure the effectiveness of proposed solutions.

In addition, in order to successfully investigate the issue of internationalization in higher education in Kazakhstan, it is necessary to analyze the relevant literature and existing research, as well as consult with experts and stakeholders such as universities, government organizations and international organizations involved in education and science.

The results were presented at the round table discussion where all participating universities were present as well as representatives from HEIs in Almaty and Astana. The suggestions from the round table discussion on the 6th March 2018 in Almaty and were included in the final report accordingly. The round table was organized by the British Council.

2.2 Modern technologies

Data from individual universities was collected, but analysed together as a group, thus the term “the Group” to represent all six universities. Each of the six universities has its own distinguished characters. And no comparison was made within the Group, instead, information provided was utilised to gain knowledge and lessons on the current status of internationalisation by higher education institutions in regional areas, particularly along the borders and the central area.

Most of students from the Group going to overseas universities in the past three years were pursuing either an undergraduate study or a master or PhD degree, with the former being slightly high. Over the three-year period, the numbers of undergraduate students are fairly stable, but postgraduate numbers vary, largely due to available funding. In comparison, the numbers for short term exchanges had been much smaller, to about one-sixth of the number pursuing a degree study.

In terms of the percentage going overseas, a weighted percentage is adopted to take into consideration of different sizes of student population in the universities of the Group, which vary over 10 thousands to 2 to 3 thousands. It is thus not a simple average of the percentage of each university in the group.

Data shows that outgoing postgraduate students take a significantly higher ratio than undergraduates do. In 2014-5, just slightly less than 10% of registered MSc and PhD students in the Group went to study overseas. This may not mean that they actually got an overseas degree in the end, as short term exchanges have also

been counted as long as students are registered for a corresponding degree. Such exchange visits provide valuable experience of the higher education system in a foreign country, and exposures to different culture as well as enhancement of foreign language capability. Though this percentage dropped in 2015/6, the figure improved in the following year, showing a recovering trend. As most of the overseas trips were financially

supported, the percentage number is highly dependent on the funding available. In comparison, the overall total percentage, where both outgoing UG and PG students are considered, is fairly stable at around 1% in the three-year run.

2.3 Data collection of internationalization in higher education

Weighted percentage of studying overseas

The vast majority of students went to Russia and East European countries to study, mainly due to language capability. While US, Germany and China appear to be the second tier destinations, probably due to the funding supports available. There is a long tail of other countries where a limited number of students went to.

More students went to Russia to pursue a postgraduate research degree, including both MSc and PhD, while fewer for short term exchanges. In contrast, short term exchanges were more significant as the purpose to other destination countries to gain an overseas exposure, e.g. US.

Funded opportunities to study overseas are provided primarily by the Government, such as Bolarshak scholarships, and others, including overseas sponsorship. Figures provided here are the total numbers of students and faculties went to overseas universities in the

past three years. The numbers include both short term visits from a few weeks, up to one year and to full PhD degree programmes of three to four years.

Short term academic visits were the majority. Opportunities for students and faculties to pursue PhD studies in an overseas university have been rather limited.

An increasing number of overseas trips from 2014-15 is presented. The vast majority of overseas student coming to study in the Group in the past three years were for a Bachelor programme. The proportion of OS students pursuing a Master or PhD degree in the Group is so small that there is a vivid contrast to outgoing students from the Group, where the numbers on postgraduate study were comparable to those on undergraduate programmes.

Destination countries of overseas study by students

Overseas student numbers by year

Numbers of funded overseas studies or visits

Weighted percentage of overseas students

Numbers of language training by the Group

An the current academic year, the Group on average provides one quarter of undergraduate courses, and roughly 20% of postgraduate courses, with part or all

elements being taught in English. For exchange programmes, it is only 1%.

Prediction for the use of English as a teaching language shows a reduction in the coming academic year. But this might be due to incomplete estimates as teaching arrangements are still being planned for the new academic year.

In the past three years, a small number of faculties in the Group were sent overseas to obtain a degree, with 19 received a Master degree, and only 2 received a PhD, which is a disappointment.

In contrast, a fair number of faculties went overseas for short term exchanges, and there is a fairly healthy trend of increase in numbers over the past three years.

This is clearly an indication of the attention by the Group to increase their faculties exposure overseas, but

funding availability or/and the possibility to allow faculties to be away from work for an extended period of time, such as pursuing a PhD. The percentage of faculty in the Group with an overseas degree is fairly low. In the whole Group, 2.2% have a PHD obtained from an overseas university and 1.4% have a Master. 7.5% faculty went to overseas on academic exchanges or training of a short term, from weeks to up to one year. There is a healthy number of joint publications by the Group faculties with overseas co-authors. Joint publications in international conferences nearly triples the number in journals. Both show a clear increasing trend, and the trend in jointly conference papers are particularly strong.

The higher education system in Kazakhstan has evolved rapidly with a significant expansion in the number of universities, both publically and privately established, which creates a very competitive demand for students in the higher education system in the country. There are also regional issues such as youth migration and funding allocation to the universities. As a result, universities are looking for ways to improve teaching programmes and to enhance research activities as part of the measures to strengthen the status of university as an education provider. Internationalisation is clearly regarded as an effective potential tool for achieving greater outcomes.

1) Have you ever studied or worked abroad?

- Yes
- No

2) How important do you think it is for higher education institutions to have internationalisation policies?

- Very important
- Somewhat important
- Not important

3) In your opinion, what are the main benefits of internationalisation in higher education? (Select all that apply)

- Exposure to different cultures
- Improved language skills
- Enhanced academic and research opportunities
- Expanded career prospects
- Other (please specify): _____

4) Have you ever encountered any challenges or obstacles related to internationalisation in higher education? If yes, please describe.

Yes, I have encountered challenges: _____

No, I have not encountered challenges.

5) How do you think higher education institutions can better support international students and staff?

Offering language support

Providing cultural orientation programs

Creating inclusive and welcoming environments

Other (please specify): _____

6) In your opinion, what can higher education institutions do to increase the number of international students and staff?

Offering scholarships and financial aid

Building partnerships with international institutions

Promoting their programs and reputation globally

Other (please specify): _____

CONCLUSION OF THE 2nd CHAPTER

Universities are interested and keen for internationalization:

All universities are keen on internationalisation and have strategies in place with partnerships and activities to different extents. All universities have an international office or a centrally operated department of similar functions. One question being raised by several universities is how to attract overseas universities' interest in collaboration. One of the key challenge universities need to consider is to provide a clear and convincing picture to potential overseas collaborators on the benefit of forming such a partnership, being for educational purposes or research. One should look beyond just academic strengths in education and research, but also regional and national culture as well as business opportunities offered to such partnerships.

Collaborations are neighboring countries focused

Probably due to the legacy of the educational system and network from the former Soviet Union era, universities have established strong connections with the neighbouring countries sharing a common ground of understanding, and the ways to conduct teaching with mutual credits recognition as well as similar quality assurance systems. Such close liaison is a valuable asset to universities and should be maintained, and if appropriate, expanded.

Nevertheless, in order to gain wider influences and recognitions, partnership should be sought, particularly in the most broadly based English speaking educational

systems over the world, including the UK, US, Canadian and Australian circles where knowledge and acceptance are more readily shared and promoted.

EU is another important region which is reasonably close to Kazakhstan, which may generate significant economic, political and cultural impacts. Collaborations should go beyond just mobility and exchange programmes but to a higher level, involving joint capacity build such as development of new master programmes to be jointly delivered. Erasmus+ has specific funding schemes to support such collaborative development.

Cost is a crucial barrier

The cost of study abroad is often deemed too high by surveyed universities. The financial implications are one of the top concerns not only to university managers but also to faculties and students interested in going abroad for degrees or experience. Cost concerns to managers also include time commitment allowed for faculties to be away from their daily work.

Language is a key driver and barrier

Students like to study abroad partially because of the language capability to be acquired, along with academic knowledge and international experience. However, language is also a source of great anxiety. Most students and faculties do not consider going abroad to study or learn often because they are not fluent in foreign languages.

New approaches are needed

The barriers to university's internationalization effort are clear: financial cost, language, time commitment, and ambiguity regarding benefits and what can

be achieved. Universities must work together with business and government to produce innovative solutions in line with what students and faculties value to provide opportunities. It is the universities' responsibility to provide the steer and encouragement. Are there new models of funding available? How can technology play a bigger role in promoting internationalization? Would TNE (transnational education) with an overseas university provide a way forward?

Access to information about opportunities to study or experience abroad need to be readily available. Also, the message that international experience benefits employment must be conveyed. With the government's new priorities to universities, much change is expected to the high education system in Kazakhstan in the next few years, in response, university's strategy in internationalization must also evolve.

Legal provisions of internationalization

State Program on Education for 2011-2020 is aimed at increasing competitiveness of education system in Kazakhstan. Integration to world education arena and achieving high level of quality of higher education that will meet labour market, industrial and innovative development needs of the country are the most important aspects in this legal framework that address internationalization. In terms of the indicators that have a direct effect on internationalization aspects, a few can be named: 2 HEIs listed in the top international ranking tables, accreditation according to international standards and publications of faculty in impact factor journals. The process of integration of education, research and industry is another positive aspect that can have a positive impact on internationalization. E-learning and internet provision in education establishments are essential elements for advancing internationalization practices. "Bolashak" program for Master's degree, doctorate degrees and research trainings is another aspect to boost internationalization in HEIs in Kazakhstan. Essential academic mobility for one academic period allows better integration into European area of higher education. Nazarbayev University experience and its dissemination is another key contributing factor.

Bolashak remains the key player on education landscape of the country. The Bolashak program in 2014 was named "The Best Scholarship Program in the World" at the international conference of the British Council of Going Global. Students studied in leading universities in Great Britain, USA, Canada, Australia, Germany, Ireland, Russia, China and other countries.

CONCLUSION

International rankings can have a significant impact on global competition. Countries and organizations often use rankings as a benchmark to measure their performance in various areas and to identify areas where they may need to improve to remain competitive. In this way, rankings can help drive innovation and progress, as countries and organizations seek to improve their performance and gain a competitive advantage.

International rankings can also influence the perceptions of investors, businesses, and individuals. A country or organization with a high ranking in economic strength, innovation, or quality of life may be

perceived as a more attractive destination for investment, talent, or customers. This can create a positive cycle of investment, growth, and innovation that can further improve rankings and competitiveness.

However, international rankings can also create a competitive dynamic that can lead to a race to the bottom. Countries and organizations may seek to achieve high rankings by lowering standards or cutting corners, which can have negative impacts on social and environmental considerations. This can create a negative cycle of competition that can ultimately harm society and the environment.

To ensure that international rankings promote positive competition, it is important to ensure that the rankings are based on a comprehensive set of metrics and data and accurately reflect the realities of a country or organization's performance. It is also important to ensure that the rankings do not prioritize short-term gains over long-term sustainability and that they promote social and environmental responsibility. Finally, it is important to promote collaboration and cooperation between countries and organizations to achieve shared goals and drive progress in a sustainable and equitable way.

Overall, research on international rankings and global competition is a critical area of study that can help us understand how to promote innovation, progress, and sustainability in today's interconnected world. Also consolidating international partnerships is a critical strategy for promoting global cooperation and achieving shared goals in today's interconnected world. By building strong relationships, working together on shared challenges, and promoting mutual understanding, we can create a more peaceful, prosperous, and sustainable world for all.

Based on this finding, it can be concluded that the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan reforms and government initiatives are being supported and are implemented successfully by the regional universities. All participating universities have internationalisation as one of the top priorities and have successful examples to share. All surveyed universities have strategies on internationalisation and have certain "pockets of excellence" in their internationalisation practice.

Universities play an important role in the society and regional economy and are important player for geopolitical context. Common language and heritage provide fertile ground for collaborations, however other collaborative opportunities with overseas countries should be developed.

While cost is a crucial barrier, but also teaching and administrative loads are barriers for establishing new and maintaining existing collaborations. Certain financial mechanisms and reduction of teaching hours are needed in order to foster international partnerships of faculties.

Language is identified as a key driver and barrier which proves the right course of the government of Kazakhstan identified in the State Programme on development and functioning of the languages in the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2011-2020 where trilingual policy is introduced and where English language proficiency is

seen as a way for integration into world education arena. Easy access to English language journals and development of research culture where the latest research in certain fields are available, read and discussed will become common in universities.

Universities in Kazakhstan must become education beacons and drivers for innovation, internationalisation and economic growth. New approaches and paradigms need to be sought, developed and implemented. In order to become number one stop for businesses to seek solutions, the curricula have to reflect business demands for professionals. The latest collaboration of the higher education sector with the National chamber of Entrepreneurs "Atameken" addresses this need. Internationalisation practices should be systematic and in line with university's priorities, needs and programmes.

Legal frameworks are in place in order to take internationalisation to a new level. Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan implements new reforms in order to be in line with recent developments in education sector. More autonomy for Kazakhstani universities provides new opportunities for internationalisation practices.

Regional development programmes are being implemented by the government and provide new opportunities for universities.

Even though competition for high school graduates is very high from major cities, Russia and OS countries, regional universities have the capacity and can offer unique programmes to occupy leading positions in their regions. The Draft Law being introduced by the government should bring some advantages to our Group universities the like in regional areas.

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